

Development of a Polymer Composite Industrial Machine

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ABSTRACT

The development of a new reinforced polymer-composite industrial machine, viz. a corrosion-resistant pump, is described. The development started with a special polymer which was selected for the required corrosion resistance to a variety of acid and alkaline media. The polymer was then combined with adequate glass-fiber strengthener, to develop a composite which would have sufficient static and dynamic load capabilities, including long-term fatigue properties. The properties of the molded composite, including both static and dynamic load capabilities and long-term fatigue load capabilities were evaluated on the finished structural elements through extensive laboratory testing and theoretical analytic approaches. Corrosion tests on both coupon samples and pump components established the corrosion-resistance for the final composite formulation.

The resulting product, a fiberglass reinforced polymer pump has the casing, cover, impeller and other basic machine and structural elements constructed out of this composite. This corrosion-resistant pump is a viable commercial product, produced in a variety of sizes, shapes and configurations, capable of the required functional operations. It is now an industrial-machine product, successfully competing against stainless steel and other exotic corrosion-resistant metal pumps in the chemical process, pump and paper, metal and mineral mining, environmental control, desalination, and other related applications.

INTRODUCTION

The chemical process industries have had a continuing need for a superior reinforced polymer-composite pump, which could combine the structural integrity of a corrosion-resistant metal pump with the superior corrosion resistance that may be achieved with an optimally designed polymer-composite system. But of course, it is well known that even today, the polymers industry -- which usually produces more materials by volume than all of the ferrous metals put together -- often critically depends upon developments that are less than a decade old. Also, as is well known, polymer-composite structures are not necessarily selected because of the low cost of the constituent materials, but because of the production-process economies that result from producing parts that can be molded to near final dimensions, which require minimal secondary manufacturing operations.

Most U.S. made metal pumps designed for the chemical process industries have, in recent years, adhered to the 1971 ANSI (American National Standards Institute) Standard B123-1, which stipulates that pumps of similar size be dimensioned for parts interchangeability in terms of mounting dimensions, location of suction and discharge nozzles, drive shaft, base plate and foundation bolts. With its long commitment to cost effectively serving the needs of the chemical process industry, Ingersoll-Rand Co. looked to the glass-fiber reinforced polymeric (GRP) materials, because of their proven record -- of combining the needed strength with chemical corrosion resistance -- in the chemical process industries for such applications as pipes, fittings, tanks, and other structures. Thus, an R&D program was initiated to develop a series of pumps (Figure 1), whose fluid-end components including the casing itself, would be made from a single GRP materials formulation, that would be strong enough to fit within the envelope of the ANSI dimensional specifications and yet would:

- o provide the needed corrosion resistance to a broad spectrum of corrosive chemical pumping situations.
- o have adequate structural integrity for the intended variety of applications.
- o have proven performance demonstrated through combined laboratory and field testing.
- o have a drive shaft design intended, specifically, to uniquely suit the stress-distribution requirements of a GRP impeller.
- o provide ease of maintenance.

Because of the well-known properties dependence of a fiber reinforced composite molded product upon the processing and manufacturing variables, actual pump components were tested for structural integrity (in contrast to depending upon coupon testing); thus, a reiterative process of design, testing, and analysis was used to optimize the structural configuration of each key component of the pump.

MATERIALS OPTIMIZATION

From manufacturing considerations of balancing production quantities against tooling costs, the time-proven compression-molding process was selected as an appropriate method. However, the selection of the final composite material had to involve the screening of many competitive resin formulations, as well as the optimizing of glass-fiber reinforcement, flow-control fillers, and other additives. For screening purposes, flat-plaque-test coupons, (152x76x6mm) conforming to ANSI/ASTM C-581, were compression molded. However, recognizing the fact that the ASTM recommended standard coupon -- containing no fillers and reinforcements, and produced by hand lay-up techniques with surface mats -- would have limited meaning for evaluating our compression-molded reinforced polymeric structures, a departure from the standard coupon formulation was made. Thus, the test coupons, for our screening tests, used

the same geometry as the ASTM standard, but included the intended production formulations. Therefore, the modified screening tests permitted the evaluation of the resin, as well as the fillers, reinforcements, and the additives that would be used in production molding of the pump components.

Using appearance (Figure 2), Barcol hardness, and flexural strength retention as criteria for the inorganic corrodants, and weight gain and thickness change for the organic solvents, as applicable criteria, a variety of representative chemical environments were evaluated at two temperature levels.

Four acid media, and one alkali medium were selected at concentrations conforming to ASTM C-581, and tested at an exposure temperature of 82C:

- 5% Nitric Acid
- 5% Sodium Hydroxide
- 15% Hydrochloric Acid
- 25% Sulfuric Acid
- 25% Acetic Acid

Additionally, sodium hypochloritic (5%) and monochlorobenzene were environments selected for testing at 49C.

Materials variables, included in the evaluation, were a number of resin formulations such as: vinyl esters, isophthalic polyesters, bisphenol-A polymer etc. Also included were various glass-fiber types, fiber pretreatments, and length of fibers (chopped randomly oriented), flow-control agents, fillers, (clay, talc, silica, wollastonite etc.) additives, and catalyst systems, as well as processing variables such as premix control, mold release agents, etc.

Ratings selected (on arbitrary scales) for specimens in terms of appearance, and strength retention, (data samples in Table I), and weight/thickness changes with organic solvents (samples in Table II) were used for screening materials/process variables. From such evaluations, a cumulative semi-quantitative value was assigned for each coupon specimen to comparative evaluation. Though somewhat subjective, this evaluation system has been found to be useful as a screening test at the Dow Laboratories over a period of some time. Additionally, comparison coupons were taken from standard compression-molded blind-pipe flanges made by FRP (epoxy and vinyl ester) pipe makers. This comparison was included because FRP pipe fittings (elbows, laterals, tees) have been extensively used in chemical process piping systems, over a period of many years, and have demonstrated a well-proven performance record. The screening test coupons from our optimized process and materials formulation compared favorably with the corrosion-resistance of the pipe-flange coupons.

Based upon these screening evaluations, Dow Chemical Company's (Derakane 470) -- a high temperature vinyl ester with a novolac backbone -- showed the best corrosion resistance performance to this wide variety of corrosive environments. In particular, Derakane 470's outstanding resistance to hydrochloric acid, and monochlorobenzene and a wide range of aromatic and aliphatic organic chemicals, was a determinant in the final selection of this resin as the composite matrix.

PROPERTIES SPECIFICITY IN A MOLDED COMPOSITE PRODUCT

Test results with coupon specimens (such as the ANSI/ASTM C-581) can have only limited significance for a molded GRP structural component, because of the difference between dispersion and orientation of the strengthening fibers in the coupon compared with that which may occur within a molded configuration of complex geometry. Recognizing the possibility of non-homogeneity in the structural fiberglass distribution, that may be introduced in the process of molding, the pump body itself was pressure tested progressively to the failure load for checking its pressure containment capability. Other tests involving casings, covers, impellers, in single-cycle and multiple-cycle testing provided

supportive data on the dispersion and orientation of the strengthening fibers achieved in these molded components. Indeed, the evolution of the finally optimized design (Figure 3) and manufacturing specifications resulted from an iterative series of design, analysis, and testing, with corrective optimization feedback, as needed.

GRP PUMP COMPOSITES

A) Casing Pressurization

Pump casings were stress coated (a thick brittle-lacquer coating), and then were internally pressurized, in order to determine the loci of maximum strain regions on the pump and the cover respectively. The pump and the cover were also separately tested, using a premachined steel cover, and a premachined steel cavity, so as to identify the weak regions in each component. Up to 30 strain gages were applied at the specific high-strain locations indicated by the stress-coat tests, and the casing and/or cover was repressurized up to 1.03×10^6 N/m² (Figure 4). Typically, the maximum measured stress in any location was well below 20.68×10^6 N/m² (using $E = 13.8 \times 10^9$). Finally, single-cycle burst tests were performed (filling the pump with liquid, and pressurizing with nitrogen from a gas cylinder); and the measured burst pressures indicated a safety factor of 3 to 6 over the specified pump maximum discharge pressure. However, when the pressure gradient within the pump is recalculated to an equivalent uniform pressure, these safety factors reach the range of 9-12.

B) Casing Fatigue Endurance

In order to determine the effects of cyclic fatigue loading on possible deterioration of the strength of the composite pump body, a cyclic hydraulic pressurizing from $0-1.03 \times 10^6$ N/m² was applied for 20,000 cycles, using fluid at RT and at 82C respectively (Figure 5). Following such a series of pressurizing load cycles, (during which no failure was indicated) the casing was burst tested and showed no loss in ultimate strength of the casing.

C) Long Term Hot-Loop Exposure

In order to evaluate the performance and reliability under simulated service conditions, a pump loop test (Figure 6) using 93C tap water (at 9×10^{-4} m³/s flow rate, on a 38x25x152mm, pump, 68.95×10^3 N/m² inlet pressure was run near shutoff for over 8,000 hours, with periodic inspections at 30, 60, 90, and 120 day intervals. At the end of 6,600 hours, only a 3% drop in performance was measured, and dimensional changes were less than 0.5%. The structural integrity of the pressure containment was determined, by burst testing after over 8,000 hrs. of pressurized operation, and was found to be unaffected. Also, the polygon drive gave quite satisfactory performance, over this entire period.

D) Nozzle Loading

The ANSI standard specifies a maximum shaft coupling deflection of .127mm under allowable nozzle loads. Based upon measured (Figure 7) nozzle loads at a radial deflection of .127mm, the GRP pump was shown to be able to withstand the specified loads allowable on equivalent ANSI metal pumps.

E) Impeller Fatigue Performance

Because of the criticality of the impeller, which is subjected to centrifugal, torque and axial thrust loads, cyclic torque and thrust loads were applied for up to 50 million cycles, simulating hydraulic loads at 93C in order to establish adequate life of this component. Of course, the long term hot loop testing also attested to the impeller performance, under prolonged hot-water pumping conditions.

F) Tapered Polygon Drive

In order to reduce high-local stress concentrations (undesirable in a polymer composite structure) such as those which would normally be experienced in a keyed joint between the GRP impeller and a steel shaft, a tapered polygon drive was specially designed for this structural component. Also, the glass-fiber distribution in this critical region was optimized through iterative testing and process modifications.

FIELD-INSTALLATION PERFORMANCE

Of course, the final proveout of any product is in its performance under real-life operating conditions. Extensive trial installations, since late 1978, have proven the performance of the GRP pump as being equal to or better than that of stainless steel pumps, operating in a variety of corrosive environments, such as:

- o a steel mill pickling acid service
 - 10% spent HCl
 - $172.4 \times 10^3 \text{ N/m}^2$
 - 60C

GRP has operated over 2 years, where alloy-20 stainless pump failed in 1 month.

- o Refinery in S.W. U.S. - H_2SO_4 service
 - 5% H_2SO_4
 - $379.2 \times 10^3 \text{ N/m}^2$
 - 71C

GRP has over 12 months service, where 316 S.S. lasted 10 days.

- o Texas chemicals plant, chlorinated septic water
 - $275.8 \times 10^3 \text{ N/m}^2$
 - 68C

GRP has performed over 18 months, where 316 S.S. lasted 2 weeks.

In many different corrosive fluid applications, the GRP pump has proven itself to be a reliable, efficient pump, and is establishing its way as a new approach to specialized industrial machinery design with fibre reinforced composite materials.

REFERENCES

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Table I

Examples of Semi-Quantitative Corrosion Coupon Ratings

Test Types	Test Media			
	NaOCl	CH ₃ COOH	H ₂ SO ₄	NaOH
I-Flexural Strength Retention				
Formulation A	58	74	100	23
" " B	81	58	77	15
" " C	83	81	41	33
" " D	88	70	100	36
II-Appearance				
Formulation A	18	6	2	21
" " B	20	12	6	23
" " C	19	3	20	15
" " D	20	6	2	17

Table II

Weight Gain and Thickness Change in Solvents

Formulation	Weight Gain	Thickness Change
A	1	1
B	1.2	2
C	1.1	1
D	0.4	1

Figure I - Molded Fiberglass Reinforced GRP Pump

Figure 2 - Top Left: Test Coupons After Exposure to Corrosive Environments
Figure 3 - Top Right: Cutaway View of GRP Pump
Figure 4 - Center Left: Strain Gaged Pressurized Casing Test
Figure 5 - Center Right: Fatigue Cycling of Pump Casings
Figure 6 - Bottom Left: Hot Loop Pump Test
Figure 7 - Bottom Right: Nozzle Load Test

